

Experiences of teachers when supporting learners with behavioural problems in the inclusive foundation phase classes of Gauteng East District

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Abstract

Different behavioural problems amongst learners pose a serious challenge in schools, and the country as a whole. The study reported on the challenges teachers face in the Foundation Phase (FP) classrooms as they deal with an array of learners with different behavioural problems which retard the progress, quality of teaching and learning and the smooth running of the school. The escalating rate of behavioural problems in schools alerted educators that indeed there is a shortage of skills competence in them to be able to handling, learners who show rampant undesirable behaviours. Misbehaving learners are fully protected by the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa (1996) and the South African Schools Act (1996) on the use of corporal punishment as a corrective measure, which to them is seen as degrading on the human dignity of the child. Many teachers and parents feel disempowered when it comes to instilling discipline in learners.

Using the qualitative method and its various data collection instruments, the researchers collected data on two schools namely, full-service and mainstream schools, with a total of 16 participants participating in. Data was collected with the use of semi-structured interviews - that targeted the deputies, FP Heads of Department, School-Based Support Teams (SBSTs) and grade heads (from grades R-3.)

The study revealed that there is a neglect in using and implementing an inclusive education policy, specifically EWP6 (DOE, 2001) and SIAS (2014). Another finding was, it seems that there is no monitoring of, and or accountability on, the implementation of policies post-training, and this had financial implication for the state resources.

It was further discovered through interactions with the participants that the support systems from the employer varied. Full service schools were prioritised on both inclusive intensive training and implementation by teachers to acquire the necessary pedagogical skills in minimising these behavioural problems in schools. There was a lack of uniformity, and divided attention in practice when supporting schools on inclusive policies and implementation. This resulted in experienced and competent teachers exiting the education system, believing that their welfare was ignored by the employer. The Department of Education has imposed numerous changes in terms of learner support, without engaging those teachers or offering professional support to ensure teachers are fully competent and functional. The discovery also indicated that failure to train teachers, immensely culminated in a failure to build inclusive classrooms, schools and society by its inhabitants due to lack of knowledge and skill competence.

Key words:

behavioural problems, foundation phase, inclusion, intensive training, intervention strategies, parental involvement, support, teachers.

Introduction and background

Negative behaviour changes amongst learners escalated post-1994 when the use of corporal punishment as an indicative to alleviate misbehaviour in the classroom, school and society at large was prohibited in terms of both the Constitution and the South African Schools Act. Behavioural challenges became a growing concern for frustrated teachers. Hard sanctions were imposed by the Education Department, through the Educational Labour Act 4 of (RSA) section 185 and Schedule 8 on Code of Good Practice and South African Council of Educators (SACE, 2011) on the teachers found inflicting corporal punishment on learners in the classroom. The SACE (2019-2020) annual report gave statistics that 38 percent of reported cases were that of teachers inflicting corporal punishment and/or assault learners, which resulted in them being struck off educators' roll or suspended for a period of time and having to pay fine depending on the severity of misconduct as per Employment of Educators Act of (RSA) section 17.

The Constitution of South Africa (RSA, 1996A, s12) and SASSA (DoE, 1996B, s10) intensely prioritised and protected the learners' needs and wellbeing, noting that inflicting corporal punishment in learners is a serious crime. The learners cannot take the responsibility for their antisocial actions or misbehaviour. Many teachers felt unprotected and, believing they are not supported by their employer which ought to put forward proper intervention strategies for use in the classroom situations. Thus, there is a gap between the intensive training which teachers receive, and the support they can offer learners when it comes to instilling the classroom discipline, particularly when using the inclusive education policy. The (RSA) inclusive education policy requires schools to accommodate all learners regardless of their different abilities and/or behaviours. Thus, designing and implementing the behavioural plan might help in the modification of the unacceptable behaviour (Shea & Bauer, 2012; Hallsworth, 2023).

The SIAS (RSA) policy could suffice after training was received and the necessary steps to identify learners' behavioural challenges could be implemented as per the inclusive policy (EWP6, 2001, DBE, 2014). The gap of lack of skills competency training could be closed through intensive training for all teachers might alleviate the current stress level amongst most experienced teachers, whom are seeking to exit the education system due to frustrations with inadequate support received from the School Management Team (SMT) and the District-Based Support Team (DBST). Most of the SMTs showed little interest in matters relating to inclusive policy which has resulted into poor monitoring

and support for teachers, as well a lack of accountability. Thus, poor support from seniors demotivated teachers and they became barriers to teaching and learning, and they developed negative attitudes and unacceptable behaviour themselves. In one of the sampled schools, this was supported by a participant who had received training, yet failed to disseminate the information gathered during such upskilling. Information sharing could give rise to teachers sharing their burdens and classroom frustrations, and helping their fellow educators to reach the common goals of providing quality education to all learners (Lave & Wenger, 1991).

Aim of the study

The aim of the study was to identify and explore the experiences of teachers in respect of supporting learners with behavioural problems in an inclusive FP classes, with the purpose of improving the quality of education for vulnerable learners who experience barriers to learning (included are family dysfunction, language issues, poverty, learning difficulties and disabilities) (DBE, 2014). By discovering the causes and effects of learners' behavioural challenges, it came evident that there is indeed a gap in the level of teachers' skills competencies in handling the related scenarios, due to poor training they receive on EWP6 (DOE, 2001) and SIAS policies. This has resulted in teacher attrition and some exited the education system with the needed experiences. Marais & Marais (2010) & Kingwill (2016) concur, adding on the experiences and frustrations of teachers who opted on exiting the education system due to frustration and depression, believing their wellness is not supported by the employer. They felt not being supported on current inclusive education policies, they also voiced that their seniors lacked any interest in inclusive matters. Nonetheless, inclusive education should never be undermined as it is defined as a system that accommodates all learners' differences, advocating education for all without discrimination (DoE, 2001, UNESCO, 1994).

There was an outcry on disturbances on smooth running of teaching and learning. According to CAPS (2011) the weekly allocated time for FP teaching and learning, which is 22h30 to 25h00 respectively. This is reduced due to unruly learners in the classrooms. Such behaviours need to be corrected before teaching and learning can commence. Where there is a lack of discipline, there is often poor learners' performance, learners' absenteeism, bullying and other learners bunking classes and many more behavioural challenges that have a negative impact on the culture of teaching and learning. It is key to equip teachers with an understanding of all-inclusive education matters, before engaging all the relevant educational stakeholders in education to work collectively as an integrated whole (i.e. family, school and society at large). Where there is greater discipline and wide buy-in, there is a better chance to fight the immoral degeneration in schools and the entire society.

According to (Marais & Marais, 2010; Nguyen, Huynh, & Kim, 2022) there is a complex relationship between the elements of any system, and they must be understood if one is to understand the system as a whole. Maguvhe (2015) and (Aas, 2022) agree, noting that there ought to be relevant support structures for all educators on the education system along with an adapted curriculum which meets the diverse needs of all learner cohorts. Inclusive education is emphasised to ensure that all learners are fully accommodated in their diverse needs. Furthermore, (Munawir, Salim & Gunarhadi, 2018) elaborate on the need for inclusive education, branding it an open, simple, learning friendly and practical approach that allows each individual with every difference to learn.

Literature review

Comparative studies were conducted for an overview of the researchers on the situation in South Africa, African countries and a few countries abroad. To that end, the researchers focused on learners' behavioural problems, behavioural management, policies outlining disciplinary measures in the school context, as well as school rules and also the intervention strategies thereof. The Constitution of S.A (RSA, 1996, s12A (1) protects the human dignity of the child. Other policies such as the ELRC reportedly also took strict disciplinary measures against those teachers who violated the legislation, even expelling those due to failure to adherence to the rule. By contrast, the DOE showed leniency towards learners who committed serious misconduct against teachers, and were only suspended for a few days, inadequate rehabilitation, or were referred to deviation programmes and then sent back to school. A case in point is Glen Vista school learner who attacked a teacher. A 14-year-old Crosby Primary School learner punched the teacher after being told to take off a jersey that was not part of a school uniform. Many cases such as these, are not reported or mentioned. Mr Panyaza Lesufi, the Member of the Executive Council (MEC) of Gauteng province, reported that 26 schools teachers had been the targets of physical abuse by the learners, with many other cases going unreported, as teachers believe their safety is under threat (Ngobeni, 2013; Shange, 2017) .

SASA (RSA, 1996B) on the other side maintains that the School Governing Bodies (SGBs) should employ alternative means to instilling discipline in their schools, by drawing up a code of conduct. This should be shared with parents and learners, so that they can offer inputs and ultimately approval of the rules thereof. Such legislation works in favour of the learners, and disempowers teachers on instilling a code of good conduct to learners hence the behaviours in schools were uncontrollable and reported daily on learners against other learners and victimised teachers. Given that the focus is on learners, many teachers feel unprotected, believing their safety and security is compromised, and calling on SACE to protect their interests (Mncube & Harber, 2013). Burton and Leoschut (2012) found that 52,1 percent of teachers had been exposed to violence by learners in Cape Town; 12,4 percent exposed to physical violence; and 3,3 percent exposed to sexual violence. Many more cases which have gone unreported are because teachers feared for their safety and others feared embarrassment and mockery as reporting played the role of not being able to discipline a child (Segalo & Rambuda, 2018).

3.1 LEARNER BEHAVIOURAL STATUS IN SOUTH AFRICA

A major behavioural challenge in this country, is a high rate of early teenage pregnancies, with 60 percent of Grade 10 learners dropping out before reaching Grade 12. Early sexual experimentation has contributed to spread of diseases such as HIV/AIDS, which has also a detrimental impact on the economy. Early school leavers contribute to the high unemployment rate, which leads to a greater reliance on government support grants. In few countries such as Turkey, 53 percent of teens reached university level, while in Brazil and Chile the numbers were 67 percent and 72 percent respectively (Kemp, Gustafson & Samuelsson, 2011; Spaul, 2015).

Burton and Leoschut (2012) and Prior, Win, Hassiotis, et al., (2023) in their study single out the following as behavioural problems: gangsterism in schools, physical fights amongst learners or with teachers, racial issues, the use and sale of illegal substances on school premises, bringing dangerous weapons to the school premises and drunkenness at the school. Many teachers and parents feel that the ill-discipline in schools is worsening by the day, and requires collaborated effort by stakeholders in the mesosystem (namely home-school-society) to come up with decisive solutions for combating

this problem. Discipline is vital for bringing back a culture of smooth running and effective teaching and learning in schools again (Sun & Shek, 2012; Prior, Win, Hassiotis, et al., 2023).

Countries such as Brazil, Turkey, the United Kingdom, Singapore and the United States have zero tolerance for misbehaviours in their schools (Sun & Shek, 2012). Their rules and regulation on accepted behaviour are clearly stated for both the teachers and learners within the school environment. Learners are monitored progressively with consistent corrective measures so that they do not transgress the school's code of good ethic. Continuous transgression of the school rules led to suspension or expulsion depending on the severity of offence. Different countries are guided by their own legislation to achieve their own expected educational goals.

According to Harber (2013) Malawi and Botswana also have identified gaps in teacher training and teachers without qualifications. Education is not compulsory for school-age learners, and classrooms are overcrowded which led to high learners behavioural problems. In Malawi, some teachers are guilty of misconduct which includes intoxication, absenteeism and sexual harassment of learners (Harber, 2013). These behavioural problems affected the quality of teaching, in one way or the other and this calls for an urgent attention by government officials. Furthermore, intervention strategies need to be devised as a matter of urgency for the quality of results (Prior, Win, Hassiotis, et al., 2023; Wei, Huang, Xia, et al., 2023). Cultural influences played a prominent role in their classroom (Garegae, 2007; Schimmelpfennig & Muthukrishna, 2023; Varadarajan, Hefny, Srivastava, et al., 2022).

Theoretical framework

The study is predicated on Jessor and Jessor's (1977) problem behavioural theory, which examines the types and causes of behavioural manifesting themselves amongst learners. Those problems are largely influenced by family factors, school factors and the social environment. Each of these is addressed below.

4.1 Family factors

These influenced a child's development negatively, if the home is dysfunctional, the family unit is broken up by divorce; there is the death of a family member; or where parenting styles are problematic e.g., with physical or sexual abuse, and drug addiction being common.

4.2 School factors

Some schools present barriers to learning, if the environment or prevailing climate is unfavourable for teaching and learning. Included here are issues such as: overcrowding in classrooms, a rigid curriculum that uses a one-size-fits-all approach; a lack of skills/competencies amongst teachers and managers; poor planning; dishonouring of periods, absenteeism; sexual abuse by teachers; continued use of corporal punishment; and a failure to implement policy guidelines which guided the schools for full functionality.

4.3 Environmental factors

Societal norms have a marked gross influence on the learners (either positive or negative) as the children learned by emulating the unacceptable ethics and values of their seniors, including undesirable behaviours such as stealing, being truant, bullying, being absent from class, not showing respect or being violent towards others and undesirable behaviours.

Methodology

The qualitative approach was used by the researchers as a form of master plan inquiry. Face-to-face interviews were used to collect data for in-depth understanding of the participants' lived experiences of challenging behaviours in learners (MacMillan & Schumacher, 2014). Teachers' experiences in FP in Gauteng East District were fully explored.

Purposive sampling was used to select a small group from a larger group with similar characteristics deemed to be knowledgeable of, and informative about the phenomenon of interest (Menter, Elliot, Hulme, Lewin & Lowden, 2011). Two local FP schools were sampled: a full-service school and a mainstream school. The aim was to gather information and to compare their schools' functionality in respect of inclusive policy, particularly regarding compliance matters, implementation, management and teacher supports. The target population was deemed to meet the criteria related to the FP teaching experience, different grade levels, gender, age, post description, highest and inclusive qualification and training received.

All the participants were females except for only one male from school A. The participants provided in-depth best information which helped the researchers and generalised results to explore and explain the phenomenon in question (Palinkas, Horwitz, Green, Wisdom, Duan & Hoagwood, 2015). The total sample comprised of 16 participants (which were 8 participants from each school).

The instruments and procedures used to gather information revolved around the semi-structured interviews, with open ended questions to explore the experiences of teachers in their classroom situations and to get in-depth inquiry. Ample opportunity was given to participating teachers to vent their frustrations and expound on their successes in their classrooms. The open-ended questions allowed for further probing and clarification on the content of study. Educational managers were also interviewed to obtain their understanding of inclusive education and the support given to teachers, based on the learners' behavioural problems, as well as the strategies used for intervention to ensure that the culture of teaching and learning remained uninterrupted and fully functional. SBST on the other side had their interview sessions to determine what frustrated them, strategies to support teachers at the school level and referrals to the district. The interaction was productive and they elaborated on the positive attitude they received from teachers and parents when support had to be instituted to the misbehaving learners.

Documents such as the school code of conduct, the behavioural management policy, classroom rules, learners' observation books, SBST entry books, of both schools' were obtained and thoroughly analysed by the researchers. Audio recordings and note-taking were used, with the participants' permission, granted by participants to ensure accurate information capturing and reliability, and to avoid the fabrication or falsification of information.

Ethical considerations

The researchers adhered to research ethics requirements. During the interactions with participants, for instance, their rights, anonymity and confidentiality were protected (McMillan & Schumacher, 2014). Pseudonyms were used to anonymise both the names of the schools and that of participants. During the open discussions, the purpose of the study was thoroughly discussed to the participants and were informed of their rights to terminate or withdraw from the study if they so wished during the process of data collection (Booyse et al., 2001). The purpose of the study and all the nitty gritty was thoroughly discussed, and the participants voluntarily accepted the participation by signing declaration form that guaranteed the confidentiality and anonymity (Delamont, 2012).

Findings and data analysis

The analysis of results is defined as a systematic process of interpreting data, to provide explanation for a single phenomenon of interest (McMillan & Schumacher, 2014).

The researchers used transcribed notes and the audio recordings made during face-to-face interviews with the participants, to collate information. The data collected were studied, analysed, simplified, clarified, interpreted in words rather than numbers, finalised and narratively linked to the research questions and the aim of the study, as recommended by (McMillan & Schumacher, 2014).

The researchers used the inductive reasoning to synthesise the data, to arrive at new ways of understanding the pieces of collected information. The data were subsequently coded into categories and is combined under themes, to construct the participants' reality, in order to make judgements on specific findings from their perspectives and to draw inferences that will add to the body of knowledge (McMillan & Schumacher, 2014).

From the findings it was apparent that behavioural challenges in schools are culturally abnormal and interfered with the smooth running of the schools. Antisocial behavioural problems violated other learners' rights to learn, and caused the disturbances in the classroom situation (Emerson, 2001). The qualitative research design was used by the researchers to engage participants to get comprehensive knowledge about the theme of study by focusing on their experiences, challenges, causes and to find the intervention strategies thereof.

7.1 Findings

School A was an inclusive mainstream school, that is led by a principle who strives to ensure diversity, and fosters maximum participation by all learners. The principal and his staff do everything in their power to address barriers to learning experienced by learners with disabilities, and render necessary support to accommodate their diverse needs in keeping with the requirements of the (DoE, 2009). SIAS-trained teachers in the school constituted 60 percent of the staff while untrained staff totalled 40 percent. There was continuous support on inclusive education matters for the newly appointed teachers. The school was fully resourced, with teachers receiving continuous intensive training from the DBE. Their training included changing learners' attitudes and behaviour to full participative learning, with a flexible curriculum, and that created an environment that was conducive to effective teaching and learning (DoE, 2001).

According to the principal of school A, there were frequent and or weekly visits from the district to discuss learners' barriers to learning and support needed. The school was at an advantage, as it received two Learner Support Educators (LSEs) on site to assist teachers in this regard, and proposing the possible intervention strategies for them. The LSEs were deployed by the Gauteng East District to work with the SBST to create the school environment which is conducive for learning.

Some participants commended the involvement of the SGB, for being engaged in all matters pertaining to the school, and for assuming the full parental roles and responsibilities including (instilling discipline in learners. The code of conduct of learners was used as a behavioural management policy, and parents were involved as a system to give their inputs on what would constitute acceptable good morals, values and ethics amongst the learners. The parents were given the code of conduct to instil discipline even at home, thereby enhancing the home-school relationship. According to the participants' point of view, it became so clear that they valued receiving intensive training, which covered different aspects of learners' behaviours and needs (DoE, 2001). All the participants commended the training they received and confirmed that they were fully

resourced, with access to files on inclusive education in the classroom that were evident and accessible.

School B was a full-service school, that accommodated learners with special needs and those without disabilities in one class, to acknowledge respect and diversity in learning (DoE, 2001). Special planning for teaching was made to accommodate different abilities through differentiation in the classroom. Most of the teachers were not trained on SIAS, and lacked pedagogical skill competence. The inadequacy of teacher training resulted in SBST being partially functional.

7.2 Biography of participants

The researchers conducted a skills audit to obtain in-depth information. Only three teachers (19 percent) of the total of 16 participants had inclusive education qualifications that intensified their knowledge on the subject. As far as school A was concerned, the quality of knowledge was improved through intensive training received from the district, in collaboration with (ELSEN) schools, where good classroom practice and all barriers to learning was shared. The school was regularly visited by the District Inclusive Support Service (DISS) for monitoring purpose, to support learners with serious barriers to learning.

Contrary to school A the participants in school B did not have inclusive education qualifications, which made them to fully depend on intensive training from the district. Of the eight participants interviewed, only one was trained on SIAS but never disseminated or shared information with the entire staff about good practises, nor monitoring by SMT or accountability.

No one from the School Management Team (SMT) attended SIAS training to monitor and support the staff on inclusive education policy implementation to meet the learners' diverse needs and to accommodate all of them. None of them had showed an interest in this inclusive education and implementation. Therefore, teachers use their own experiences in teaching, and dealing with, learners with behavioural problems.

The semi-structured questions were used for in-depth inquiry. Below is what emerged from the findings.

8.1 Theme 1: Foundation Phase learners' behavioural challenges- teachers' experiences

The participants shared their frustrations and experiences of the classroom situation, which in their view had a negative impact on the quality of teaching and learning, and on their outcome on performance (for which they were held accountable). The behavioural problems they identified included bullying, theft, vulgarity, ADHD, late-coming, truancy, noisiness, failure to do school-related activities and a massive lack of morals and values. In both schools, bullying was identified as being the most serious and prevalent problem, and that aggression included pushing, kicking, biting, and stabbing others to inflict pain and many more. In one of the school, a psychosocial problem arose where a learner brought to school a pepper spray and sprayed another learner in class, disrupting teaching and learning. This affected other classes because the safety of the other learners was violated. Environmental factors had an influence on the learners, with some displaying behaviour learnt at home or the society and brought it to school. This traumatised both the learners and all staff. That school never received the psychological support needed to deal with the issue.

The disturbances observed by teachers in their classrooms had violated the teaching and learning time which, according to CAPS (DBE, 2011) should be between 22h30 to 25h00 hours a week. The participating teachers commented that they had to correct such misdemeanours, before resuming their lessons in their classrooms. The Constitution Act 33 of 1996A (RSA Parliament, 1996A) opened

the door of ill-discipline in schools across the country. A participant added that learners use their rights as an advantage to disrespect the teachers, their elders and community at large. The participating teachers admitted to feeling frustrated and felt disempowered by the decision of the new dispensation. SASA (RSA, 1996B) maintains that teachers should use alternative ways to instil discipline in their schools, by drawing up a code of conduct which educators can customise to suit the challenges confronting their individual schools.

They were dissatisfied about the changes made without supporting teachers by upskilling and reskilling them. According to a skills audit conducted by the researchers, only a few teachers (i.e. 19 percent of the total of 16 participants) had acquired inclusive qualification through self-development private studies, and was able to use the knowledge gained to apply SIAS procedures to identify learners with massive challenges to learning. One of the participants was able to support a learner who showed symptomatic ADHD by applying individual strategies/programmes, to meet the learner's special needs, in keeping with the Gauteng vision and mission which had to ensure that "every learner feels valued and inspired in our innovative education system" (DoE, 2018).

They were able to follow the protocol of SIAS referral; by completing the Support Need Forms (SNA) to SBST until to District-Based Support Team (DBST) for further referral to ensure that learners were supported at an early stage, and that parents be engaged so that support given at school be extended at home. Late-coming was managed by both schools with the parents' assistance, through instilling discipline. In one school (school B), the SGB played a prominent role in managing negative behaviour through the use of the code of conduct, which was communicated to parents, with consensus being reached on the expected behaviour to be instilled in the learners. In this way the family-school relationship was built to overcome behavioural problems.

In School A the use of extra curriculum was prevalent; learners were taught in totality and multi-intelligences amongst learners were valued immensely. The school promoted maximum participation in and outside of the classroom, in line with the goals of the Education White Paper 6 (EWP6) (DoE, 2001). There are days where learners competed against other schools by playing chess, which kept them busy from loitering in the streets, and promoted critical problem-solving skills at a young age. They also made use of soul buddies, facilitated by Soul City mentors, to train learners from grade 4-7 in leadership and discipline in schools. These learners worked collectively and collaboratively with teachers, on assisting them to restore the discipline in the school. As Jessor and Jessor (1977) state, the behavioural problems should be described according to their nature, frequency, severity and duration.

8.2 Theme 2: Effects of behavioural challenges on quality of teaching and learning- policy implementation

The code of conduct and classroom rules served as tools, employed by both schools as part of the behavioural management policy, to alleviate serious behavioural challenges. These tools were explained to learners, to remind them of their expected behaviour in the school and classroom environments. In this respect, Skinner (1953) maintains that good performance should be rewarded, as it has the potential to increase the probability of acceptance and it extinguishes undesirable behaviour.

The participating teachers reported being frustrated by the continuous bad behaviour shown by some learners, compelling them in schools; they were disturbed daily by learners' misdemeanour as they had to correct undesirable behaviour, rather than teaching – a finding which matched that of (Singh, 2014). In the participants' view they no longer enjoy the profession, anymore and resorted to exiting the education system. Some participants indicated that they ended up screaming to the learners, in an attempt to restore order in class.

The controls imposed by the Curriculum Management Model (CMM) and School-Based Assessment (SBA) in both schools were mentioned as a barrier to learning, and had increased the challenges faced in the classroom. It contravened with both EWP6 (DOE, 2001) and SIAS (DOE, 2014) which require learners diversity to be accommodated by means of curriculum adaptation and adjusted teaching methods, with the purpose of changing the learners' attitudes and meeting all their educational needs, while allowing them to feel valued and inspired in the classroom environment EWP6 (DoE, 2001, DOE, 2014). It is imperative that the district subject facilitators work as a system with policy implementers so that when instruction had to be executed by teachers are the same without confusion caused. Facilitators wanted teachers to cover the curriculum on set dates whereas the inclusive policy emphasise the diversity and differentiation that need enough time to meet the learners' needs.

Other participants pointed to teachers' attitudes towards teaching and learning, as the causes of learners' misbehaviour. They came to class unprepared, followed a rigid curriculum with no diversity or inclusivity, undertook poor classroom management, answered phone calls during learners' contact sessions, failed to honour periods, were absent from school, and did not attend training – all of this and many more. These attitudes affected the culture of learning and teaching.

8.3 Theme 3: Support systems that the teachers need to reinforce positive behaviour in their classrooms

A point of departure was on SIAS training, to close the skills gap of incompetency amongst implementers. EPW6 (DOE, 2001) policy reinforces the training and development of teachers, to enable them to implement the teaching strategies that will strengthen their profession and allow them to handle classroom challenges. Most of the School Management Team (SMT) members participating in this study were found not to be interested in inclusive education and policy implementation. They were found to have neglected their job description that of supporting their subordinates as well as performing their roles diligently as mentioned in Personnel Administrative Measures (PAM, 2016).

There was poor accountability from the principals, as chief executive officers of the schools, whose core duty was to advise on policies, and to ensure that policy implementation is adhered to. Continuous district support is imperative, as gathering a skills audit to identify the percentages of teachers which did not receive training, or to accommodate the newly appointed teachers. The planned emotional and psychological support by the employer, in the form of workshops to boost the morale of teachers to remain positive and fight the battle in instilling discipline in schools is crucial.

Marais and Meier (2010) advocate that there should be collaboration, and communication and the sharing of ideas on all-inclusive education matters, including barriers to learning. The system theory was used to understand the complex relationship between home-school-society and how should each interact with the other, to resolve school-related challenges that are in crisis with the quality of teaching and learning (Kingwill, 2014; Marais & Meier, 2010). As regards home-school support, the

parenting style has a marked influence on the development of a child's behaviour, especially in dysfunctional families, and this may give rise to cognitive and psychological disorders (Burger, 2017; Woolfolk & Perry, 2013).

8.4 Theme 4: Intervention strategies for behavioural management-future resolutions

Possible intervention strategies were discovered during the interviews with the participants, and seek to ameliorate the learners' behavioural problems and improve the teachers' attitudes. The following recommendations were made:

Class size; class size should be reduced, to allow learners to receive individual attention. That would permit a teacher to identify the cause of misbehaviour, and to provide the support needed. The learner-teacher ratio should be considered. Overcrowding should by all intense and purpose be addressed.

Training should be prioritised, especially for the senior managers, as drivers of the curriculum. This will enhance the implementation of inclusive education, to promote differentiation and accommodate learners' diverse needs.

SGB training to be a second priority, allowing members to understand their roles and to fully engage with entire parents and other stakeholders, to assist in creating disciplined and purposeful learning environment that is built on respect and trust (DoE, 1996)

No underage learners should be admitted; In some cases, learners are admitted throughout the year and mostly are underage learners to increase the school enrolment (it finally increase the principal's salary but that is counterproductive.)

Colleges of education and, universities (through national policy makers) should incorporate inclusive education as a compulsory study. Curriculum in schools should be flexible to accommodate diverse learners' needs and the behavioural challenges they face, in addition to outlining support strategies.

Teachers should use reinforcements to reward a positive behaviour to encourage the acceptable behaviour for all learners. The reward system is also encouraged by Skinner (1953) who is a theorist of classroom management, who states that tokens extrinsically motivate learners to behave in an acceptable way.

Life Skills subject should be reinforced in the Foundation Phase, especially outdoor activities which shape the learners in their totality (i.e. physically, socially, mentally and emotionally) to improve the quality of life and help building a peaceful, prosperous and democratic South Africa (DBE, 2018; Landsberg, Kruger & Swart, 2011). Learners learn to behave appropriately at school and in the society at large, by understanding themselves and how to relate to others, sharing views respectfully and communicating meaningfully.

Interdepartmental structures, such as the Department of Social Services, the Department of Health, the Department of Education, policy makers, teachers and external support systems such as non-governmental organisations (NGOs) and other stakeholders with expertise should work in tandem to collaborate, communicate and share their knowledge, expertise and inputs to deal with unwanted behaviour in classrooms affecting teaching and learning in our schools and around the country (DoE, 2001).

Behavioural management policy should be drawn up in collaboration with parents and other stakeholders and be understood by, all its constituents in a school. It should be contextualised to address the different behavioural challenges of learners, at school outlining different intervention

strategies and sanctions (if transgressions are observed, in addition to stipulating levels of its severity).

DISCUSSION

School A

On analysis of results from the data collected on both schools; the researchers discovered that both schools differ on their status from one being a full-service and the other being an ordinary mainstream school. The former school benefited from training and development on policy matters by the employer and its partners and also on service delivery in accordance with EWP6 (2001) and SIAS (RSA, 2014). This made it a fully functional school, with evident systems in place on policy and curriculum delivery, thus meeting all the expectations and targets of the employer. Thus, the school was able to deal with teachers' stress levels, since the SMT was continuously hands-on, and fully supported teachers in dealing with learners' behavioural challenges, or any situations which are learner centred. Clear plans and intervention strategies were in place for dealing with unruly behaviours and diverse learning modes at school. All the policies were accessible, on request, by the researchers and correlated for feasibility of what had been said by participants' observations at large. The few behavioural incidents were minimal and manageable with the support the Department of Education, SMTs, teachers, SGBs and entire parental involvement and the nearby community, all of whom worked as a system to fight the behavioural crisis that affected many schools nationwide in the interests of the learners. The school's best practises were commendable, deserving of a learning curve even to the researchers. Such schools should be awarded recognition for having a positive influence on other schools, by collaboration and sharing good practises i.e. SMTs, teachers, SGBs and the nearby community.

School B

The researchers' point of departure for the school is gathered information on SMT in particular, and conducted a teachers' skills audit, which revealed that there was low percentage of teachers who have been trained in inclusive education. This calls for an immediate action, before more teachers exiting the system due to frustration. Some of them indicated to have reached pensionable age. To that end, the training of the principal and SMT in particular, should be prioritised as they were the ones to develop and to drive policies which serve as the effective guiding tools to minimise challenges that the school might have experienced. Team work in all school planning was minimal, thus the school experienced significant challenges that will require emergent attention in the form of continuous support and monitoring from the district.

It emerged, from the interviews, that even teachers contributed grossly to the behavioural challenges which learners presented through their unbecoming conduct and attitudes towards teaching and learning. Teachers were absent from class but albeit being present at school.

In Gauteng, only a few schools declared as full-service schools which received ample opportunity in the form of support from the district, to advance inclusive education implementation. A high percentage of main stream education schools are disadvantaged and do not receive the unwavering support by the district. For that reason, some of the teachers and managers have developed negative attitudes that resulted to behavioural challenges.

Recommendations

This article sought to close the perceived skills capacitation gap which is frustrating to teachers who are at the stage of failing to instil discipline to learners in their classrooms. It is recommended that intensive professional developmental strategies/or programmes, be put in place in the form of training. This should be perceived as the development of necessary competencies needed to address different and severe learning barriers and training has the power to strengthen the education support services (DoE, 2001).

SMTs are key role players and drivers of the curriculum, therefore, it is recommended that members undergo the intensive training, which will make them accountable in their roles, as outlined in the PAM (2016). School performance is likely to improve by engaging seniors to disseminate information, as per protocol, to the staff at large.

The failure of the SMT to support teachers in terms of the new system of education and on policy implementation is detrimental to them to develop the attitude and behaviours that affected the teaching and learning. Having the comparative study on both schools it became prevalent that Continuous support, in the form of training and information sharing, brought about a change of mind-set amongst the teachers in School A and strengthened their expertise and skill competence on their job description.

It is highly recommended that schools collaborate with each other to share both their frustrations and best practises, to advance teaching and learning, and produce outstanding outcomes.

It is further recommended that overcrowding in schools should be addressed, to minimise the learners' misbehavioural problems in the classrooms. The DOE should consider the teacher-learner ratio (especially in township schools, which are no-fee schools and fully financially depended on the department). The X Model schools still charge fees, and can reduce learner classroom size by creating SGB posts. Learners' behaviour becomes more manageable if classroom sizes are reduced.

Labour Unions should work alongside the employer to support the needs of teachers, in developing their members (i.e. capacity building, and empowerment) to strengthen their teaching strategies in the classroom and on expected behaviours in schools to protect their jobs. SACE as an organisation, that protects the welfare of the teachers, should assist in protecting the teachers as their affiliates. They also need to capacitate them as regards roles and responsibilities as agents of change, and as positive role models in education.

Conclusion

A gap has been identified, which can be closed through intensive training and upskilling and reskilling of teachers, to improve the quality of education. This needs an urgent attention. A skills audit should be conducted, since training has serious financial implications. Failure by the authorities (seniors from national to school level) to monitor the implementation of inclusive education once state resources are utilised for training, will yield a negative return on investment. However, if implementation is monitored and good results are yielded, then the resources will be used efficiently and effectively, to bring about change in schools. Finally DOE will then have invested in training to overcome what has become the educational crisis for many stressful teachers and is affecting the quality of teaching and learning.

In South Africa, education is guided by legislation, including the Constitution of S.A and policies. Inclusive policies such as EWP6 (2001) and SIAS (2014) should be prioritised, to promote Education For All (EFA) (UNESCO, 2009) which is a human rights issue, whereby all learners have a right to equal

access to education and accommodated in their diverse needs. Educational stakeholders should always strive to accomplish the Gauteng vision where “every learner will feel valued and inspired in our innovative education system” (DoE 2018). As MEC Mr Panyaza Lesufi indicated, a commitment is needed to transform schools to become learner-centred catering for all learners’ needs by offering equitable and quality education which is devoid of labelling (GDE, 2016).

There should be collaboration and information sharing amongst all three types of schools (i.e. LSEN, full-service and mainstream) which have their own strategies of offering support to learners with diverse needs, allowing them to learn from each other’s expertise and best practises. Singh (2014) emphasises that networking is key, and a means of peer support and information sharing on good practises. The DOE should offer psychological support, in allowing teachers to vent their classroom frustrations, and upskilling them so that the wellbeing of learners and (teachers) is well taken care of. Teachers should receive the same attention from the department.

As Segalo and Rambuda (2018) note, teachers are under attack by the learners; some have retaliated in defence and lost their jobs, whilst others felt too embarrassed to report this issue. Safety and security in schools should never be compromised, and require immediate attention from all the stakeholders. In addition to that schools should be free zones from violence, and should offer a safe haven for all learners (Musu-Gillete Zhang, Wang, Kemp, Diliberti & Oudekerk, 2018).

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